

Aquatic Fungi from Tapi District, Gujarat.

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Abstract –

Fungi are the most diverse group of eukaryotic organisms. Mycologists define true fungi as heterotrophic, eukaryotes. Fungi characteristic with cell walls of β -glucan and chitin with absorptive mode of nutrition.

This paper reports the occurrence of three Aero – aquatic fungi species as *Helicomyces colligatus*, *H. roseus* and *H. torquatus* as well as two Coelomycetes fungi species as *Chaetospermum indicum* and *Robillarda sessilis*, from the foam samples collected from different streams of Tapi District, Gujarat state (India).

The data provides information on the range of distribution of these fungi in India. Descriptions and illustrations are provided.

Introduction - Presently, the ‘fungi’ as a mega-diverse group span into three kingdoms, mostly belonging to the kingdom “Fungi” (Eumycota), while others are classified in the kingdom “Protozoa” and kingdom ‘Chromista (Straminipila)’ (Cavalier-Smith, 1998; James et al., 2006).

The fungi play a dominant role in the decomposition of plant detritus (Borlocher, 1992 a, b). Fallen tree trunks, branches and twigs regulate stream dynamics by increasing the retention of organic matter. They used to enhance the fast litter decomposition in aquatic ecosystem and nutrients release. Decomposition of these woody substrates is important in nutrient cycling and the role of wood decay is determined by both physical and biological factors (Harmon et al., 1986).

Taxonomic account –

Aero – aquatic fungi - These are found in low-oxygen environments like in stagnant water or mud. These fungi produce conidia at the air-water interface, which are then released into the air or float on the water surface. These fungi produce three-dimensional shaped conidia, such as globose, crown-shaped, or helicoid.

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Genus *Helicomyces* Link

Ges. Naturf. Freunde Berlin, Mag.3: 21 (1809).

The genus was introduced by Link in 1809 with *H. roseus* Link as its type species. The species of the genus are characterized by having; Colonies are effuse to arachnoid or tuberculate, white to pinkish, or becoming brownish in age. Mycelium is immersed or superficial, composed of branched, septate, hyaline to dilute fuscous hyphae. Conidiophores are lacking or formed as short, lateral branches of the repent mycelium. Conidiogenous cells are mono- or polyblastic, producing conidia from the apex, or synchronously and /or successively from short denticles. Conidia are hyaline, dry, hygroscopic, frequently uncoiling in water. Conidial filament is coiled 1-8 times, usually in one plane to form a disk-like body, but sometimes in three planes and resembling a loosely coiled spring; basal cell attached eccentrically; conidial secession schizolytic. The genus is represented by 12 species (Zhao et al., 2007; www.mycobank, org, accessed on 1 June 2016).

Helicomyces colligatus R.T. Moore

Mycologia, 46: 89 (1954). [Figure no.1]

Conidia - loosely coiled 1-2 times, acrogenous, dry, hyaline, hygroscopic, multi-septate at maturity, each cell containing one large 83 vacuole or two smaller ones; filament tapering at both ends, the basal end 3.5 μm broad, conidial filament enlarging to 8 μm broad in the middle and becoming slightly less at the distal end, easily broken into segments; diameter of coils 50-60 μm .

Material examined - Conidia in foam sample, Gugalapani river (at Kuchhalivel); V. S. Patil; 08 August 2014. Conidia in foam sample, Doswada dam (at Rampura); V. S. Patil; 17 August 2013.

Distribution in India - KK- Conidia in foam samples (Ramesh, 2002); GJ- Conidia in foam samples (Borse et al., 2015); MH - Conidia in foam sample (Patil et al., 2015d)

Remark - The fungus was first time recorded from Gujarat.

Helicomycetes roseus Link

Ges. Naturf. Freunde Berlin Mag. Neuestern Entdeck. Gesammten Naturk., 3: 21(1809)
[Figure no.2]

Conidia - hyaline, white to pinkish in mass, attached eccentrically, frequently with hyaline secondary conidia, 25-60 μm in diam. Conidial filament 4-5 μm in diam., multi-septate, tapering to an enlarged, obliquely flattened basal cell, coiled $2\frac{1}{4}$ -3 times.

Material examined - Conidia in foam sample, Mindhola river (at Titva); V. S. Patil; 15 October 2013. Conidia in foam sample, Gira river (at Vati); V. S. Patil; 27 January 2013.

Distribution in India - KK- On Submergedleavesand in foam samples (Rajashekhar and Kaveriappa, 2003); UK- Conidia in water samples (Arya and Sati, 2012); MH - Conidia on submerged decaying wood (Patil et al., 2015c); GJ- Conidia in foam sample (Borse et al., 2015b).

Remarks - The measurements and descriptions of conidia are agreed with that of *H. roseus* as given by Zhao et al. (2007). Therefore, it is assigned to that species. This is an addition to the fungi of Gujarat.

Helicomycetes torquatus L.C. Lane & Shearer

Mycotaxon.19: 291 (1984). [Figure no.3]

Conidia- hyaline, multi-septate, dry, coiled 1.8 to 2.8 times, 104 – 132 μm diam., end cells broadly spatulate, end of basal cell bearing flattened attachment scar. Conidia in water hydrophilic and floating or unwinding to assume a torque-like or sigmoid form, 372 – 528 x 5 – 7 μm . conidial filament 5-7 μm in diam., multi-septate.

Material examined - Conidia in foam Samples, Mindhola river (at Bajipura); V. S. Patil; 15 December 2013.

Distribution in India - KA- Conidia in foam samples (Ramesh, 2002); MP -Conidia in foam samples (Patil et al., 2014c); MH-Conidia in foam samples (Patil et al., 2015b); GJ- Conidia in foam samples (Borse et al., 2015b).

Remark - This is reported for the first time in Gujarat.

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Coelomycetes fungi - These are a large, artificial group of fungi characterized by producing asexual spores (conidia) inside a cavity-like structure called a conidiomata, which can be a spherical pycnidium or a disc-shaped acervulus. They are found in diverse environments, acting as plant pathogens, endophytes, or saprobes. It was treated as a distinct group i.e. Deuteromycotina.

Genus Chaetospermum Sacc.

Syll.Fung., 10: 706(1892).

Patouillard in 1888 described a fungus *Tubercularia chaetospora* Pat. from a decaying grass. Saccardo in 1892 erected a new genus, *Chaetosporium*, for *T. chaetospora* Pat. and named it *C. tubercularioides* (Pat.) Saccardo. Smith and Ramsbottom (1913) reverted to the epithet *chaetosporium* in accordance with the international rules of nomenclature. de Fonseka (1960) studied morphology of the said fungus. For genus description refer Smith and Ramsbottom (1913) and Sutton (1980). Pycnidia are white to dirty white, slimy, shining, superficial, globose to subglobose, non-ostiolate, separate or in small groups, measuring from 600-1000 µm in diam., wall of the pycnidium 38-57 µm in thickness, outer cells compactly arranged, inner once loosely woven. Conidiophores arise from the inner surface of pycnidium, conidiophores hyaline, simple or branched towards the tip, measuring from 30.4-38 x 3-4 µm.

Chaetospermum indicum Talde

Indian Phytopath., 11: 288 (1981). [Figure no.4]

Conidia - apical, unicellular, hyaline, fusiform or oblong, protoplasm vacuolated, tips rounded, measuring from 34.2-41.8 x 7.2-11.4 µm, appendages unseptate, long and are present at both ends, towards the distal end appendages 4-5 in number, measuring upto 75 µm in length, appendages 154 towards the proximal end 1 or 2 in number, generally shorter than distal end appendages.

Material examined - Conidia in foam sample, Ukai dam (on Tapi river at Ukai); V. S. Patil; 6 October 2014.

Distribution in India – MH- Conidia on stem (Talde, 1981).

Remarks - The description and measurements of conidia are agreed with that of *C. indicum*

Talde (1981). Therefore, it is assigned to that species. This is reported for the first time in Gujarat.

Genus *Robillarda* Sacc.

Michelia, 2: 8 (1880).

The genus was introduced by Saccardo (1880), with *R. sessile* (Sacc.) Sacc. as the type species. The genus is characterized by having, Pycnidia are solitary or gregarious, separate, subglobose, unilocular, immersed, ostiolate, glabrous. Conidiogenous cells are holoblastic, ampulliform, hyaline, originating on the inner wall of the pycnidium.

Robillarda sessilis (Sacc.) Sacc.

Syl. Fung., 3: 408 (1884); = *Pestalotia sessilis* Sacc., *Michelia*, 1: 261 (1878); [Figure no.5]

Conidia - 9-11 x 3.5 μm , oblong, one-septate, constricted at the septum, pale olivaceous, smooth-walled; with a three hyaline bristles, 14 x 1 μm . 155

Material examined - Conidia in foam sample, Gugalapani river (at Mandavipani); V. S. Patil; 1 September 2012.

Distribution in India – AP - Conidia in foam (Manohara. and Murthy, 1981).

Remarks - The description and measurements of conidia are agreed with that of *R. sessilis* (Sacc.) Sacc. Therefore, it is assigned to that species. This is reported for the first time in Gujarat.

Aero – aquatic fungi

Figure no. 1

Figure no. 2

Figure no. 3

Coelomycetes fungi

Figure no. 4

Figure no. 5

Figure no. 1 *Helicomyces colligatus*, Figure no. 2 – *H. roseus*, Figure no. 3 – *H. torquatus*, Figure no. 4 - *Chaetospermum indicum*, Figure no. 5 - *Robillarda sessilis*.

Conclusion – Aquatic fungi species, *Helicomyces colligatus*, *H. roseus* and *H. torquatus*, *Chaetospermum indicum* and *Robillarda sessilis* are first time reported from Gujarat. Therefore, these species are an addition in Gujarat microbiome.

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Abbreviations – AP – Andhra Pradesh, AS – Assam, GJ – Gujarat, KK- Karnataka, KL – Kerala, MH – Maharashtra, MP -Madhya Pradesh, TN – Tamil nadu, UK – Uttarakhand.
FAA – Formaldehyde, Fig. – Figure, μm - micrometer.